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Entrepreneurial Attributes Among Postgraduate Students of a Pakistani University

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ABSTRACT

This research examines the entrepreneurial characteristics among the student of University of Sargodha. The main task was to explore the entrepreneurial characteristics of the graduate students. Two hundred students from different departments returned complete questionnaires. To increase the representation, random sampling was selected. Findings revealed that self-efficacy, efficiency and commitment and entrepreneurial inclinations were the most important factors. The research showed that majority of the students have characteristics to become an entrepreneur and they showed positive response. However demographic factors have a minor impact on entrepreneurial attributes. The entrepreneurial attributes can be increased by offering certain courses which helps in increasing entrepreneurial attributes.

KEY WORDS: *entrepreneurship attributes, students*

Introduction

In these times of economic crisis, we are taken by the surprise by the fact that more and more people are inclined toward setting up their own ventures in the world of entrepreneurship. This is also crucial for the

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economy and has positive impacts over individual and economy as well. People decides to become an entrepreneur due to many reasons like need for financial independence and security, having frustration with their current workplace and career, strong desire for achievement and willingness to invest their resources and having ability to take risk.

Entrepreneurship is a key driver of economic growth and job creation. It provides many people with career opportunities that better fit their preferences than waged employment. One of the most important is entrepreneurship skills. Motivated people need the right skills to identify entrepreneurial opportunities and to turn their entrepreneurial projects into successful ventures.

There are certain personality characteristic that leads to successful entrepreneurs and these attributes are need for independence and achievement, internal locus of control, to involve in certain risks, self-confidence, to complete tasks with commitment, team building and to work under team and pressure (Martinez & Vila, 2007; Ramayah & Harun, 2004).

A researcher can distinguish entrepreneur from non-entrepreneur through many personality characteristics. When researchers investigate the matters that increase the entrepreneurial attitude, they saw that achievement, motivation and self-image play a great role (Pillis & Reardon, 2007).

Entrepreneurial characteristics among students are significantly contributed by educational programs. It is also being investigated by the research that certain university students are attracted towards entrepreneurship due to various educational programs. Significant improvement was seen in students entrepreneurial attributes when they were asked to participate in entrepreneurial educational (Schroder and Rodermund, 2006; Soutaris, Zerbinati and Al-Laham, 2007; Zhao, Seibert and Hills, 2005). There is a lot of contribution made by these educational programs in developing entrepreneurial attributes among students (Wilson, Brown, Anderson & Galloway, 2003).

It is also being acknowledged by the government that enterprise and innovation are driving force behind innovative change and job creation. Governments are encouraging the introduction of enterprise into the curriculum because it has much influence upon higher education. For developing and testing their entrepreneurial skills, students are calling for

opportunities. Industry is looking for an element of entrepreneurial creativity in its top class graduate recruits (Gibb, 2008).

This paper explores three factors self-efficacy, efficiency and entrepreneurial inclinations as entrepreneurial attributes among post graduate students of university. Based upon the literature the study set to examine the entrepreneurial attributes toward adopting entrepreneurship as a career choice among postgraduate's students of University of Sargodha, Pakistan..

The strength of the entrepreneurial class is usually visible in the entrepreneurial attitudes of university students. However, no considerable research work on the entrepreneurial attitudes of the university students has so far been published from Pakistan. This article will investigate entrepreneurial attributes among post graduate's students of University of Sargodha, Pakistan.

Literature Review

The development of entrepreneurship has become a vital function of universities. Personality characteristics, demographic factors and situational factors do not play a significant role in predicting that whether an individual is attracted towards entrepreneurial activities. Intention plays a major role in determining that whether someone has entrepreneurial inclinations or not (Krueger et al 2000).

Self-efficacy is the belief that one is capable of performing in a certain manner to attain certain goals. Self-efficacy is an individual's internal belief on his ability that whether he can perform a certain task. Self-efficacy is based on individual's internal confidence that his abilities can convert his skills into outcome (Bandura, 1989, 1997).

Many researches have been conducted to explain the relationship between self-efficacy and career preferences. These researches shows that those individuals who have self-confidence and internal belief on their abilities can more easily convert their ideas into actions. An internal belief of one's abilities leads an individual to become a successful entrepreneur. These researches have also shown that individuals who have higher entrepreneurial self-efficacy have a high desire to become a future entrepreneur. (Chen et al., 1998; DE Noble et al., 1999; Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000; Scott & Twomey, 1988; Segal, Borgia, & Schoenfeld, 2002; Wang, Wong, & Lu, 2002).

A research was conducted by Bird (1988) and Vozikis (1994) and they clearly argued that self-efficacy has a major impact in selection of entrepreneurial career. They also concluded that when a person has high level of self-efficacy and has ability to set goals, than his chances of entrepreneurial actions will increase. (Boyd and Vozikis, 1994).

Many researches have been conducted to explain the relationship between entrepreneurial inclination and demographic factors (for example Koh, 1995; Koh, 1996; Reitan, 1997; Breen, 1998; Lin, Picot et al., 2000; Dunn, 2004; Smith, 2005; Veciana, Aponte et al., 2005 Kirkwood, 2007). It has been investigated that an individual would be highly inclined towards entrepreneurship if he has a good influence by family and personal experiences (Koh 1996; Mazzarol, Volery et al., 1999; Kirkwood, 2007).

A theory was presented by McClelland (1975) to explain the entrepreneurial effectiveness. The major basis of this theory was the role of motivation and achievement. The major purpose of presenting this theory was to explain the relationship between effectiveness and leader's behavior. In entrepreneurial inclinations major contributory factors are achievement motivation and self-image (Pillis & Reardon, 2007).

It is proved by research that entrepreneurial attitudes of university students significantly affected by educational programs. It is being concluded that hidden entrepreneurial potential of students stimulated by educational programs (Wilson, Brown, Anderson & Galloway, 2003).

There are certain personality characteristic that leads to successful entrepreneurs and these attributes are need for independence and achievement, internal locus of control, to involve in certain risks, self-confidence, to complete tasks with commitment, team building and to work under team and pressure (Martinez, Mora & Vila, 2007; Ramayah & Harun, 2005; Rodermund, 2004).

Hypothesis of Study

H1: There is a significant positive correlation between 'efficiency and commitment' and entrepreneurial inclination.

H2: There is a significant positive correlation between self-efficacy and entrepreneurial inclination.

H3: 'Self efficacy' and 'efficiency and commitment' significantly explain the variance in entrepreneurial inclination.

Methodology

This research has been conducted in order to explore entrepreneurial attributes among the students of University of Sargodha, Sargodha. For this purpose a sample of 220 questionnaires was filled from the University of Sargodha, Sargodha which is one of the well renowned universities of Pakistan. As frequencies of demographics factors of sample are shown in frequency table (Table 1). The questionnaire for this research was adopted from the study (Ramayah and Harren, 2005). In which 7-point agree-disagree Likert-type scale was used for assessing entrepreneurial intention among the students of University Sains Malaysia. This scale was largely concerned with need for achievement, locus of control, self-efficacy, instrumental readiness, subjective norms and entrepreneurial intentions. For this scale the reported reliability value was 0.85. The language and content of the items were adapted by keeping local requirements in consideration.

The questionnaires were filled from the students of different departments of the university. From total of 220 questionnaires, 200 completely filled questionnaires were returned, 8 questionnaires were lost during the process and the remaining 2 were wrongly filled. For conducting this study the data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The questionnaires were filled in the month of April, 2010. The questionnaire consisted of the total 35 questions which were classified according to the variables of this study, the first 5 questions were related to demographic variables from which 1 question was about the class of respondent, 1 was about the gender of respondent, 1 was related to respondent father's education level, 1 was about respondent father's occupation and 1 was related to residence of respondent.

The questionnaires were filled from 62 male and 128 female respondents. The five-point Likert-type scale was used ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Descriptive statistics and the comparison of mean have been used to study the response of the sample. The Cronbach's Alpha revealed the result for the overall homogeneity between the variables of this research and the items of scale used in this research to measure the variables. A correlation analysis was used to study the relationship between the variables such that this analysis studied the positive relation of all the independent variables (efficiency and commitment and self-efficacy) with the dependent variable

(entrepreneurial inclination). Regression analysis was used in order to test the hypothesis for this research.

Frequencies

Table 1: student class

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Masters	89	46.8	46.8	46.8
	Bachelors	101	53.2	53.2	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 shows that in whole sample, 46.8% respondents were master’s students while 53.2% were bachelor’s students. In other words out of 190 students 89 were doing masters and 101 were bachelor’s students.

Table 2: Student Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	62	32.6	32.6	32.6
	Female	128	67.4	67.4	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Above table 2 shows that in whole sample, 32.6% respondents were male and 67.4% were female. In other words out of 190 respondents 62 were male and 128 were female. In our research, the proportion of female respondents was greater than male.

Table 3: Student's father education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No education	8	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Primary	27	14.2	14.2	18.4
	Secondary	48	25.3	25.3	43.7
	Higher	53	27.9	27.9	71.6
	Secondary				
	Other	54	28.4	28.4	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows that in our research study, fathers of 4.2% respondents have no education, 14.2% have primary level education, 25.3% have secondary, 27.9% have higher secondary and 28.4% were included in other category. In other words out of 190 respondents fathers of 8 respondents have no education, 27 have primary, 48 have secondary, 53 have higher secondary and 54 are in other category.

Table 4: student's father occupation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Private sector employee	31	16.3	16.3	16.3
	Public sector employee	56	29.5	29.5	45.8
	Self-employed entrepreneur	50	26.3	26.3	72.1

Table 4 shows that in our sample of research, fathers of 16.3% respondents are private sector employee, 29.5% are in public sector, 26.3% are self-employed, 15.8% are retired, 3.2% are unemployed and 8.9% are in other category.

Table 5: Student's residence

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Urban	109	57.4	57.4	57.4
	Rural	81	42.6	42.6	100.0
	Total	190	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 shows that in whole sample, 57.4% respondents are residents of urban areas and 42.6% are of rural areas. In other words out of 190 respondents 109 are living in urban areas and 81 are in rural areas.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Descriptive Statistics - Descriptive Analysis

Table 6: Descriptive Analysis

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Efficiency and Commitment	190	3.4638	.55330
Self-Efficacy	190	3.5649	.50906
Entrepreneurial inclination	190	3.5842	.61949
Valid N (leastwise)	190		

Above table 6 shows that the mean of efficiency and commitment is 3.4638, mean of self-efficacy is 3.5649 and entrepreneurial inclination mean's is 3.5842.

Comparison of Mean

*Table 7: Entrepreneurial inclination * student class*

Student class	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Masters	3.4708	89	.65108	1.70	4.80
Bachelors	3.6842	101	.57511	2.00	4.80
Total	3.5842	190	.61949	1.70	4.80

It is evident from the above table 7 that there is no significant influence of student class upon dependent variable entrepreneurial inclination because both masters and bachelors have same mean 3.4708 and 3.6842 respectively.

*Table 8: Entrepreneurial inclination * student gender*

Student gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Male	3.5839	62	.67755	1.70	4.80
Female	3.5844	128	.59213	1.90	4.80
Total	3.5842	190	.61949	1.70	4.80

It is evident from above table 8 that both male and female are equally inclined toward entrepreneurship. Because the mean of male 3.5839 is almost similar to female mean 3.5844.

*Table 9: Entrepreneurial inclination * student's father education*

Student's father occupation	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
No education	3.7500	8	.83495	2.30	4.70
Primary	3.2556	27	.64411	1.90	4.60
Secondary	3.6146	48	.61298	1.90	4.60
Higher Secondary	3.5358	53	.68052	1.70	4.70
Other	3.7444	54	.44368	2.80	4.80
Total	3.5842	190	.61949	1.70	4.80

It is evident from the above table 9 that students whose fathers have no education and those whose education is in other category are more inclined towards entrepreneurship and those respondents whose fathers have secondary and higher secondary are equally inclined. Respondents whose fathers have primary education are least inclined as compared to others.

*Table 10: Entrepreneurial inclination * student's father occupation*

Student's father occupation	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Private sector employee	3.5968	31	.47643	2.80	4.40
Public sector employee	3.4839	56	.65886	1.70	4.60
Self-employed entrepreneur	3.7280	50	.59420	2.20	4.80
Retired	3.4233	30	.60611	1.90	4.30
Unemployed	3.4167	6	.82805	2.30	4.50
Other	3.8118	17	.66321	1.90	4.60
Total	3.5842	190	.61949	1.70	4.80

It is evident from the above table 10 that respondents whose fathers' occupation is in other category are more inclined towards entrepreneurship because its mean is highest as compared to others. Students whose fathers are public sector employee, private sector employee and are retired are equally inclined towards entrepreneurship because their mean is nearly the same.

*Table 11: Entrepreneurial inclination * student's residence*

Student's residence	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Urban	3.6413	109	.64982	1.90	4.80
Rural	3.5074	81	.57113	1.70	4.80
Total	3.5842	190	.61949	1.70	4.80

It is evident from the above table 11 that the categories of both respondents living in rural and urban areas are equally inclined towards entrepreneurship because the mean of both categories is nearly same

Inferential Statistics

Reliability Analysis

Table 12: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.797	29

Table 4 data tells us that 190 Respondents were used in the calculation of Cronbach's Alpha. The obtained alpha score is 0.797 which indicates that the scale has good internal consistency (reliability).

Correlation

Table 13: Correlations

		Efficiency and Commitment	Self- Efficacy	Entrepreneurial inclination
Efficiency and Commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	.503**	.500**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	190	190	190
Self-Efficacy	Pearson Correlation	.503**	1	.479**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	190	190	190
Entrepreneurial inclination	Pearson Correlation	.500**	.479**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	190	190	190

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

H1: There is a significant positive correlation between ‘efficiency and commitment’ and entrepreneurial inclination.

Table 13 indicates that there is positive correlation (R: 0.500) between ‘efficiency and commitment’ and entrepreneurial inclination which is also significant at 0.000 level. Therefore we accept the H1.

H2: There is a significant positive correlation between self-efficacy and entrepreneurial inclination.

Table 13 indicates that there is positive correlation (R: 0.479) between self-efficacy and entrepreneurial inclination which is also significant at 0.000 level. Therefore we accept the H2.

Regression

H3: ‘Self-efficacy’ and ‘efficiency and commitment’ significantly explain the variance in entrepreneurial inclination.

Table 14: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.565 ^a	.319	.312	.51378	1.829

^a Predictors: (Constant), Self-Efficacy, Efficiency and Commitment

^b Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial inclination

Table 15: ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	23.170	2	11.585	43.888	.000 ^a
Residual	49.363	187	.264		
Total	72.533	189			

^a Predictors: (Constant), Self-Efficacy, Efficiency and Commitment

^b Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial inclination

The results in Table 14 indicate that there is a positive correlation (R: 0.565) between the independent variables ('self-efficacy' and 'efficiency and commitment') and the dependent variable i.e. entrepreneurial inclination. The value of Durbin-Watson statistic (1.829) also falls within the acceptance range therefore indicating that there is no autocorrelation among the variables being studied. Similarly the ANOVA table 15 shows that the F-statistic value of 43.888 is significant at 0.000 level. Therefore we accept H3.

Table 16: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
I (Constant)	.917	.290		3.166	.002
Efficiency and Commitment	.389	.078	.347	4.975	.000
Self-Efficacy	.370	.085	.304	4.362	.000

^a Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial inclination

Table 16 indicates the value for Adjusted R Square (0.319) which shows that the independent variables ('self-efficacy' and 'efficiency and commitment') explain 31.9% of variance in Entrepreneurial inclination. Similarly the Beta values for both efficiency and commitment (0.347) and self-efficacy (0.304) are significant at 0.000 and 0.000 levels. It can also be observed that among the two independent variables being studied the variable efficiency and commitment has a greater influence on entrepreneurial inclination as it has the highest Standardized Beta Coefficient ($\beta=0.347$) which is also significant at 0.000 level.

Discussion and Conclusion

Our research reveals that positive entrepreneurial attributes are present among majority of university students. The characteristics of self-efficacy has more influenced on entrepreneurial inclinations than efficiency and commitment. There was a partial effect of students' father education on his/her entrepreneurial attributes. The demographic variables such as gender, class and father occupation, residence has no significant effect on students' entrepreneurial attributes.

Action Implications

Entrepreneurship has been found to be vital part of economy and it is main driver of economy in the whole world. Entrepreneurship provides self-sufficiency and in this changing environment of the world the knowledge of entrepreneurship has a great importance. In Pakistan, there is strong need of increasing entrepreneurial activities.

In Pakistan, entrepreneurial development is not yet fully developed. In this university the authorities should pay strong attention for the development of entrepreneurial activities. The entrepreneurial attributes can be increased by offering certain courses which helps in increasing entrepreneurial attributes. So, such courses should be introduced which encourage entrepreneurship. Government of Pakistan has indicated that very less percentage of students get an appropriate job after their graduation. Now-a-days a majority of unemployed people are either Master or Bachelor degree holders. Entrepreneurship creates wealth for the nations and boosts up the economy. So, the entrepreneurial education should be made compulsory.

This research will be helpful for the future researchers and it will increase the research works. Other countries have developed their economy through entrepreneurial education. So, it should also be developed in our country with the support and help of Government.

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Preduzetnički atributi postdiplomaca sa Univerziteta u Pakistanu

APSTRAKT

Ovo istraživanje ispituje preduzetničke osobine studenata Univerziteta u Sargodhi. Glavni zadatak je bio da se istraže preduzetničke osobine diplomiranih studenata. Dve stotine studenata iz različitih fakulteta su vratili popunjene upitnike. Da bi se povećala reprezentativnost, bio je izabran slučajni uzorak. Rezultat istraživanja je pokazao da su samoeфикаsnost, posvećenost i preduzetničke sklonosti bili najvažniji faktori i da većina studenata poseduje osobine za preduzetništvo. Međutim, demografski faktori imaju slabi uticaj na preduzetničke attribute. Preduzetnički atributi mogu biti unapređeni kroz određene kurseve koji pomažu u usavršavanju preduzetničkih osobina.

KLJUČNE REČI: *preduzetnički atributi, studenti, postdiplomci, Pakistan*

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